

BARRIERS OF EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING -A STUDY AMONG MOTHERS OF INFANTS AGED 6-12 MONTHS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breast milk is the ideal source of nutrition for infants, providing essential nutrients and protective antibodies that safeguard against common childhood illnesses. Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF)—defined as feeding the infant only breast milk for the first six months—is critical for reducing infant morbidity and mortality. Despite its known benefits, the prevalence of EBF remains suboptimal in many regions, including Tamil Nadu. To assess the knowledge and practices related to exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months, estimate the proportion of exclusively breastfed infants up to six months, and identify barriers to EBF.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study included 250 mothers attending the pediatric OPD at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital from February to July 2024. Data were collected through structured questionnaires via personal interviews. Inclusion required informed consent and infants aged 6–12 months. Exclusion criteria included medical contraindications to breastfeeding. Data were analyzed using SPSS v27.0.

Results: Most mothers were aged 26–30 years (47.6%), with 28% having primary school education. A majority (74.8%) were stay-at-home mothers, 96% were married, and 67.2% were multiparous. Institutional deliveries occurred in 92%, with 82% having vaginal births. Breastfeeding was initiated early by 76%, and 88.4% adhered to EBF guidelines by avoiding water. Antenatal counseling and postpartum education were provided to 90% and 92% respectively, though postnatal follow-up was low (68%).

Conclusion: While knowledge and practice of EBF were generally good, barriers such as delayed initiation, use of substitutes, limited paternal involvement, and poor postnatal follow-up persist. Targeted education and family engagement are essential to improve EBF practices.

Keywords: Exclusive breastfeeding, maternal knowledge, infant nutrition, antenatal counseling, postnatal care, breastfeeding practices.

Introduction:

Breast milk is the ideal food for healthy growth and development of newborns and infants. Breast milk serves as the newborn's initial and natural source of nourishment and energy, playing a vital role in promoting healthy growth during the early months of life. In addition to supporting development, it also significantly contributes to reducing the risk of illness and death during infancy.^{1,2} It is enriched with antibodies that helps and protects infants from common childhood illness such as diarrhoea and pneumonia, 2 primary cause of infant mortality.³⁻⁵

Exclusive breastfeeding is defined as breastfeeding without introduction of other foods or liquids not even water before 6 months of age with exception of drops or syrups of vitamins, mineral supplements and medicines.³ According to NFHS-5 (2019 -21) 63% of children under age 6 months are exclusively breastfed in india and only 55% in Tamilnadu compared to WHO and UNICEF 2030 target of atleast 70%.⁶ Median duration of exclusive breastfeeding is 2.9 months in india.³

Scaling up of breastfeeding results in reduction in overall infant mortality rate , neonatal mortality and infection related death.⁷ Substantial evidence from both developed and developing nations highlights the numerous advantages of breastfeeding for infants, young children, and mothers. However, despite its proven benefits, the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) is declining across both settings. Currently, only about 38% of infants under six months in developed countries are exclusively breastfed, and merely 39% of children aged 20 to 23 months continue to benefit from ongoing breastfeeding.^{8,9}

Breastfeeding is a maternal behavior influenced by various factors, including demographic characteristics, socioeconomic status, religious beliefs, and cultural traditions. However, there is a notable lack of scientific research addressing the discrepancies between awareness and actual practices related to exclusive breastfeeding, particularly among urban and rural mothers in central India, as well as the factors that influence these behaviors. The aim of the study is to assess the knowledge and practices related to exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months, to estimate the proportion of infants who were exclusively breastfed up to six months of age, and to identify the barriers faced by mothers in practicing exclusive breastfeeding during this period.

Material & Method:

This descriptive survey was conducted as a cross-sectional and prospective study. A total of 250 mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months attending the pediatric outpatient department (OPD) at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Center were included. The sample size was calculated based on the NFHS-5 report, which states that the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding for children under six months in rural areas of Tamil Nadu is 65%. By allowing a 10% relative error and maintaining a 95% confidence level, the minimum required sample size was 220. Accounting for an anticipated 10% dropout or non-response rate, the final sample size was increased to 250.

The study population comprised mothers of infants between 6 to 12 months of age who visited the pediatric OPD during the study period from February 2024 to July 2024. Participants were recruited using a random sampling technique. The inclusion criteria were mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months who attended the pediatric OPD and were willing to provide informed written consent for participation. Exclusion criteria included mothers with contraindications to breastfeeding (e.g., undergoing treatment with anticancer drugs), those with acute or chronic illness, babies with congenital anomalies, and mothers who did not consent to participate.

Prior to data collection, approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC). The mothers were approached, briefed about the study, and informed written consent was secured. A structured questionnaire was developed to collect relevant data, which included socio-demographic details, obstetric history, and breastfeeding history. The data were collected through personal interviews using this questionnaire.

Statistical analysis: All the data were collected in proforma and entered in excel sheet. The data were summarized in table as frequency and percentage. The data were analyzed using SPSS v27.0 operating on windows 10, and for all statistical purpose a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result: Present study included total of 250 participants fulfilling inclusion criteria. With majority were in age group of 26-30yrs (47.6%) followed by 24% in 31-35yrs and 22% were in 18-25yrs of age.

Table 1: Demographic details of the mothers			
		Frequency	Percentage
Age in years	18-25	55	22.0
	26-30	119	47.6
	31-35	60	24.0
	>35	16	6.4
Educational status	Post graduate	5	2.0
	Graduate degree	39	15.6
	Higher secondary	41	16.4
	High school	28	11.2
	Middle school	45	18.0
	Primary school	70	28.0
	Illiterate	22	8.8
Occupational status	Stay at home	187	74.8
	Working	60	24.0
	Student	3	1.2
Type of family	Joint family	102	40.8
	Nuclear family	148	59.2
Marital status	Married	240	96.0
	Separated	8	3.2
	Widow	2	0.8
Gestational score	Primi	82	32.8
	Multi	168	67.2
Antenatal clinic attended	Yes	240	96.0
	No	10	4.0
Place of delivery	Health facility	230	92.0
	Home	20.0	8.0
Mode of delivery	Vaginal	205	82.0
	Caesarean section	45	18.0
Postnatal clinic attended	Yes	170	68.0
	No	80	32.0

In terms of educational status, the majority of mothers had primary school education (28%), followed by middle school education (18%) and higher secondary education (16.4%). A smaller proportion were graduates (15.6%), while 11.2% had studied up to high school, and only 2% were postgraduates. Notably, 8.8% of the participants were illiterate. Regarding occupational status, a significant majority of mothers (74.8%) were stay-at-home mothers, while 24% were employed and only 1.2% were students. In family structure, 59.2% of participants belonged to nuclear families, while 40.8% lived in joint families. Most of the mothers (96%) were married at the time of the study, whereas 3.2% were separated and 0.8% were widowed. When analyzed by gestational score, multiparous women constituted 67.2% of the sample, and primiparous women made up 32.8%. Antenatal clinic attendance was reported by 96% of mothers, showing good antenatal care coverage, while 4% did not attend any antenatal clinics. With respect to the place of delivery, the majority (92%) delivered in health facilities, while 8% had home deliveries. Regarding the mode of delivery, vaginal birth was the most common (82%), whereas caesarean section accounted for 18% of deliveries. Attendance at postnatal clinics was lower, with 68% reporting participation and 32% not attending postnatal follow-up.

Table 2: Showing knowledge and practice of exclusive breast feeding among the mothers

		Frequency	Percentage
Breastfeeding initiated immediately	Yes	190	76.0
	No	60	24.0
Whether advice about importance of exclusive breast feeding during Antenatal period	Yes	225	90
	No	25	10.0
Whether advised about latching, proper positioning of Baby in postpartum period?	Yes	230	92.0
	No	20	8.0
Who explained the importance of Breast feeding	Nurse	80	32.0
	Family member	45	18.0
	Doctors	105	42.0
	None	5	2.0
	Others	15	6.0
Whether Husband knows the importance of Breast feeding	Yes	155	62.0
	No	95	38.0

Did you give water for the baby in initial 6 months	Yes	29	11.6
	No	221	88.4
Type of milk substituted	Cow milk	22	8.8
	Tin milk	5	2.0
	Milk powder	5	2.0
Any illness for the baby during 6 months / Hospitalized	Yes	48	19.2
	No	102	80.8

A majority of the mothers (76%) reported initiating breastfeeding immediately after birth, while 24% did not initiate it promptly. Antenatal counseling regarding the importance of exclusive breastfeeding was provided to 90% of the mothers, reflecting good awareness efforts during pregnancy. Postnatally, 92% of the mothers received guidance about proper latching and positioning, indicating strong postpartum support. When asked about who educated them on the importance of breastfeeding, 42% of mothers mentioned doctors, followed by 32% who were guided by nurses, and 18% by family members. A small portion received information from other sources (6%) or none at all (2%). Regarding spousal involvement, 62% of the mothers reported that their husbands were aware of the importance of breastfeeding, while 38% were not, suggesting the need for more inclusive family education. Concerning feeding practices, 88.4% of mothers did not provide water to their babies in the first six months, aligning with exclusive breastfeeding guidelines, while 11.6% admitted to giving water. Among those who provided milk substitutes, cow's milk was the most commonly used (8.8%), while tin milk and milk powder were used by 2% each.

Discussion:

The present study aimed to assess the knowledge and practices related to exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months, to estimate the proportion of infants exclusively breastfed up to six months, and to identify the barriers faced by mothers in adhering to exclusive breastfeeding. A total of 250 mothers who met the inclusion criteria participated in the study. The majority of the participants were in the age group of 26–30 years (47.6%), followed by 24% in the 31–35 years group, and 22% were aged between 18–25 years. In terms of educational status, most mothers had received primary education (28%), followed by middle school (18%) and higher secondary education (16.4%). A smaller proportion were graduates (15.6%) or had studied up to high school (11.2%), while only 2%

were postgraduates. Notably, 8.8% of the participants were illiterate. Regarding occupation, a significant number of mothers (74.8%) were homemakers, while 24% were employed, and 1.2% were students. Family structure analysis revealed that 59.2% lived in nuclear families, while 40.8% belonged to joint families. Most of the mothers (96%) were married at the time of the study, with 3.2% separated and 0.8% widowed.

In another study by Shylla B et al., among the participants, 36% (65 mothers) were aged between 24 and 29 years. In terms of education, 28.18% (51 mothers) had completed primary schooling, 2.2% (4 mothers) held postgraduate degrees, and 10.5% (19 mothers) were illiterate. A large proportion, 72.4% (131 mothers), were stay-at-home mothers. Most belonged to nuclear families (60.8%, or 110 mothers), and the majority were married (94%, or 170 mothers), with only one participant (0.5%) being widowed. Regarding parity, 44.75% (80 mothers) had two to three children. A high proportion of mothers (96.7%, or 175 out of 181) had attended antenatal clinics, and 91.7% delivered in health facilities. Vaginal delivery was the most common mode (81.2%), and 67.8% of the mothers returned for postnatal follow-up care.¹⁰

In study by Sahu B et al., the majority of mothers were aged 21–25 years (55.2%), with most residing in rural areas (76.4%). Hindu religion was most common (60.4%), followed by Muslims (35.2%). Most families had 4–5 members (60%), and nearly all participants were married (99.2%). Educational status showed that 35% were illiterate, while the rest had varying levels of formal education, with only 3.6% being postgraduates. Overall, the study population was predominantly young, rural, married women with moderate family sizes and diverse educational backgrounds.¹ In another study by Suresh S et al., the maternal characteristics from the study indicate that a significant majority of the mothers (80.5%) were between 20 and 30 years of age, while 19.5% were older than 30 years. In terms of educational status, more than half of the mothers (54.8%) were graduates or had higher qualifications. Additionally, 33.5% had completed secondary or higher secondary education. A smaller proportion had education below the 10th standard (9.5%), and only 2.3% of the mothers were illiterate. This suggests that the study population largely consisted of young and well-educated mothers.¹¹

Another study by Debnath F et al., the demographic profile indicates that the majority of mothers (52%) were aged 22 years or younger, while 48% were older than 23. Most participants (88%) identified as Hindu. In terms of caste distribution, 45% belonged to

Scheduled Castes (SC), and 36% to Scheduled Tribes (ST). Regarding maternal education, 58% had education up to the primary level, and 11% were illiterate. Paternal education levels were slightly higher, with 66% having studied up to primary and 18% being illiterate. Socioeconomic status was predominantly low, with 85% of families falling into the lower category. A slight majority (53%) of families lived in joint family setups. In 34% of households, the father was identified as the major earner. Nutritional assessment based on BMI showed that 11% of mothers were underweight (BMI <18.5 kg/m²), while 36% had BMI in the normal or overweight range (23–24.9 & ≥25 kg/m²). These findings highlight a population characterized by young age, low educational attainment, socioeconomic challenges, and a high prevalence of joint family structures.⁷

Obstetric history showed that 67.2% of mothers were multiparous, while 32.8% were primiparous. Antenatal clinic attendance was high, with 96% reporting regular visits, indicating good antenatal care utilization. Most mothers delivered in health facilities (92%), and only 8% had home deliveries. Vaginal delivery was the predominant mode (82%), whereas 18% underwent caesarean section. Postnatal clinic attendance, however, was lower, with only 68% attending follow-up visits and 32% not participating in postnatal care.

Study by Sahu B et al., documented that over half of the mothers (51.4%) had two children, while 37.8% had one child, 8.8% had three, and only 2% had more than three children. In terms of antenatal care (ANC) visits, a majority (58.2%) had fewer than three visits, while 41.8% had three or more. Despite this, only 40.4% of the mothers received breastfeeding counseling during ANC visits, whereas 59.6% did not. Regarding delivery, half of the mothers (50%) delivered via caesarean section, 47.2% had normal vaginal deliveries, and 2.8% underwent assisted instrumental deliveries. Among caesarean deliveries, spinal anaesthesia was used in 66.4% of cases, while 33.6% were conducted under general anaesthesia; none received epidural anaesthesia. As for the sex of the babies, 55.8% were male.¹

In terms of knowledge and counseling related to exclusive breastfeeding, 90% of mothers received antenatal counseling regarding its importance, and 92% were guided postnatally on proper latching and positioning techniques. When asked about the source of breastfeeding education, 42% of mothers mentioned doctors, 32% were educated by nurses, 18% by family members, 6% received information from other sources, and 2% reported receiving no education at all. Regarding spousal involvement, 62% of mothers stated their husbands were

aware of the importance of breastfeeding, while 38% were not, suggesting a gap in family-inclusive health education.

In study by Shylla B et al., the findings revealed that a significant proportion of mothers, specifically 69.6%, possessed adequate knowledge about exclusive breastfeeding. Additionally, an even higher percentage—95.58%—were aware of the recommended duration for exclusive breastfeeding.¹⁰ In study by Sahu B et al., The study revealed that 46% of mothers initiated breastfeeding within the first hour after delivery, and 47.4% were aware that exclusive breastfeeding should continue for six months. However, only 39.8% intended to breastfeed up to 24 months. While 54.8% believed breastfeeding benefits both mother and baby, 45.2% did not. A majority (61%) felt breast milk is better than formula. Awareness about storing breast milk varied, with 47.8% knowing it can be refrigerated for 1–2 days. Knowledge gaps were evident: only 40.8% knew milk secretion increases with frequent feeding, and 38.6% thought breastfeeding could continue during medication. Additionally, only 39% would breastfeed when sick, and even fewer during the baby's illness. Most (79.2%) believed HIV-positive mothers should not breastfeed. While 57.6% acknowledged breastfeeding enhances bonding, many mothers held misconceptions—39.2% felt it affects body shape, 20.2% viewed it as old-fashioned, and 43.6% found public breastfeeding embarrassing. Over half (56.8%) thought it interferes with work. On a positive note, 64.8% agreed that breast milk is pure and cost-free. The main sources of breastfeeding information were relatives (40.2%), followed by doctors/health workers (34%), and media (25.8%).¹

Concerning breastfeeding practices, a majority of mothers (76%) initiated breastfeeding immediately after birth, while 24% did not. A large proportion (88.4%) did not provide water to their babies in the first six months, adhering to exclusive breastfeeding guidelines, whereas 11.6% did provide water. Among those who gave milk substitutes, cow's milk was the most common (8.8%), while tin milk and milk powder were used by 2% each. These findings reflect generally good awareness and practice of exclusive breastfeeding, although gaps in postnatal follow-up, spousal education, and the continued use of water and milk substitutes highlight areas where additional education and support are needed.

A study conducted by Vijayalakshmi et al. (2014) identified common reasons for early weaning, which included perceptions of insufficient breast milk, the use of feeding to soothe the baby, and the belief that breast milk alone does not meet the nutritional needs of a growing infant.¹² Similarly, Ella et al. (2016) reported that factors such as emotional stress,

monotony associated with continuous breastfeeding, and pressure from mothers-in-law contributed to early cessation.¹³ Additionally, Tekle's study in South Africa (2015) on barriers to exclusive breastfeeding found that many mothers believed breast milk alone was inadequate, fearing it would leave the baby hungry, hinder adaptation to complementary foods later on, and fail to ensure the child's strength and health.¹⁴

Conclusion:

The present study aimed to assess the knowledge and practices related to exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 6 to 12 months, estimate the proportion of infants exclusively breastfed up to six months of age, and identify the barriers faced in maintaining exclusive breastfeeding. The findings revealed that most mothers had a fair level of knowledge and demonstrated generally positive practices, such as early initiation of breastfeeding and refraining from giving water or supplements during the first six months. Antenatal counseling and postpartum support were widely received, particularly from healthcare professionals, contributing to improved awareness. However, some mothers still delayed breastfeeding initiation or introduced substitutes, indicating gaps between knowledge and practice. Additionally, limited spousal involvement and reduced postnatal clinic attendance emerged as notable barriers. Overall, while exclusive breastfeeding was practiced by a majority, efforts must be strengthened to address remaining challenges through continued education, enhanced postnatal support, and greater involvement of family members, especially spouses, to ensure sustained and widespread adherence to exclusive breastfeeding practices.

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